

Assessing the Impact of Anemia in Non-Communicable Diseases at a Tertiary Care Center

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Abstract:

Background: Anemia, a significant global health issue, disproportionately affects individuals with non-communicable diseases (NCDs) such as diabetes, hypertension, and cardiovascular and respiratory conditions. The coexistence of anemia and NCDs exacerbates disease severity, reducing physical capacity and worsening clinical outcomes. Despite its importance, limited data exist on the burden of anemia among NCD patients in tertiary care settings in India.

Aim: This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence, severity, and factors associated with anemia in patients with NCDs at a tertiary care center in Patna, India, to inform targeted interventions.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted from April 2023 to March 2024 at a tertiary care hospital. A total of 100 patients diagnosed with NCDs were recruited. Data on demographics, clinical history, and laboratory parameters were collected. Anemia was classified based on WHO criteria into mild, moderate, and severe categories. Statistical analysis was performed using SPSS version 23.0 to assess associations between anemia severity and demographic or clinical variables.

Results: The predominance of anemia in the study population was 100%. Moderate anemia (50%) was most prevalent, followed by mild anemia (35%) and severe anemia (15%). Diabetes mellitus (30%) and hypertension (28%) were the most common NCDs. Significant predictors of severe anemia included female gender ($p = 0.02$), rural residence ($p = 0.01$), and NCD duration >10 years ($p = 0.02$). A significant negative correlation was observed between hemoglobin levels and NCD duration ($r = -0.42$, $p = 0.01$).

Conclusion: The study highlights the high burden of anemia among patients with NCDs, with moderate anemia being the most common severity. Female gender, rural residence, and prolonged disease duration were key predictors of severe anemia. These findings underscore the need for integrated care to address anemia in NCD management.

Recommendations: Routine anemia screening and targeted interventions for high-risk groups, particularly females and rural populations, are essential. Comprehensive management of anemia in patients with NCDs can improve clinical outcomes and reduce healthcare burdens.

Keywords: Anemia, Non-Communicable Diseases, Prevalence, Predictors, Integrated Care.

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Introduction

Anaemia, defined as a deficiency in the number or quality of red blood cells or haemoglobin levels below the WHO thresholds, remains a major global health challenge [1]. Affecting approximately 1.62 billion people worldwide, anaemia is particularly prevalent in low- and middle-income countries, with women of reproductive age and young children being the most affected groups [2]. Recent reports highlight that anaemia prevalence in India has worsened, with data from the National Family Health

Survey-5 (NFHS-5) indicating that 67% of children aged 6 to 59 months and 57% of women aged 15 to 49 years are anaemic [3]. This alarming trend underscores the need for targeted interventions to address the underlying causes and risk factors.

Simultaneously, NCDs such as diabetes mellitus, cardiovascular diseases, chronic respiratory diseases, and cancers have emerged as the leading causes of morbidity and mortality globally. These conditions account for 71% of all deaths worldwide,

with India contributing significantly to this burden [4]. Approximately 65% of deaths in India are attributed to NCDs, reflecting their profound public health impact [5]. The coexistence of anaemia and NCDs presents a dual burden that can exacerbate disease severity and clinical outcomes, as anaemia reduces oxygen delivery to tissues, impairing organ function and overall physical capacity [6].

The mechanisms linking anaemia and NCDs are multifactorial. Chronic inflammation associated with NCDs can lead to anaemia of chronic disease, characterized by altered iron metabolism and reduced red blood cell production. Furthermore, medications commonly used in NCD management, such as metformin for diabetes, have been linked to vitamin B₁₂ deficiency, a known cause of anaemia [7]. Inadequate dietary intake, poor healthcare access, and other socio-demographic factors compound this issue, particularly in resource-limited settings like India.

Despite the growing recognition of the interplay between anaemia and NCDs, there is a lack of comprehensive data on the burden of anaemia in patients with NCDs in tertiary care settings in India. This study aimed to evaluate the prevalence, severity, and factors associated with anaemia in patients with NCDs at a tertiary care centre in Patna, India, to inform targeted interventions

Methodology

Study Design: This is a hospital-based cross-sectional observational study.

Study Setting: The study was conducted at a tertiary care hospital over a period of 12 months, from April 2023 to March 2024. The hospital's outpatient and inpatient departments served as the primary sources for participant recruitment.

Participants: The study will include 100 participants diagnosed with non-communicable diseases. Participants will be selected based on specific inclusion and exclusion criteria to ensure the validity and reliability of the findings.

Inclusion Criteria

1. Adults aged 18 years and above.
2. Patients diagnosed with NCDs such as diabetes mellitus, hypertension, cardiovascular diseases, or chronic respiratory diseases.
3. Individuals with confirmed anaemia, defined as haemoglobin levels below 13 g/dL in males and below 12 g/dL in females, as per WHO criteria.

4. Participants who provide informed consent to participate in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

1. Pregnant or lactating women.
2. Patients with active infections, inflammatory diseases, or acute illnesses.
3. Individuals with a history of blood transfusions in the last three months.
4. Patients with known haematological malignancies or primary blood disorders.

Bias: Selection bias will be minimized by randomly recruiting participants from outpatient and inpatient departments. Standardized data collection protocols will be used to reduce information bias. Data will be collected by trained personnel to ensure consistency and accuracy.

Data Collection: Data will be collected using a structured questionnaire and clinical investigations. The questionnaire will include demographic information, clinical history, and details about the NCD diagnosis. Laboratory investigations will include haemoglobin levels, complete blood count (CBC), iron studies, and renal function tests.

Procedure: Eligible participants will be identified from the outpatient and inpatient departments. After obtaining informed consent, demographic and clinical data will be recorded. Participants will undergo a detailed clinical examination, and laboratory tests will be performed as part of routine investigations to confirm anaemia and its severity. All data will be recorded in a pre-validated data collection form.

Statistical Analysis: Data will be entered into Microsoft Excel and analyzed using SPSS Version 23.0. Descriptive statistics such as mean, median, and standard deviation will summarize the demographic and clinical data. The chi-square test will be used for analyzing categorical variables, while t-tests or ANOVA will compare continuous variables. Correlation analysis will evaluate the relationship between anaemia and clinical parameters of NCDs. A p-value of <0.05 will be considered statistically significant.

Results

This study included 100 participants diagnosed with non-communicable diseases (NCDs) and anaemia. The results focus on demographic and clinical characteristics, anaemia severity, and associations between anaemia and NCDs. Statistical analyses provide further insights into correlations and predictors.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics

Variable	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	60	60.0

Female	40	40.0
Age (years)		
18–30	8	8.0
31–50	32	32.0
51–70	45	45.0
>70	15	15.0
Residence		
Urban	70	70.0
Rural	30	30.0

The majority of participants were male (60%) and aged between 51–70 years (45%). Most were from urban areas (70%), reflecting the population accessing the tertiary care centre.

Table 2: Clinical Characteristics of Participants

Non-Communicable Disease	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Diabetes Mellitus	30	30.0
Hypertension	28	28.0
Cardiovascular Diseases	20	20.0
Chronic Respiratory Diseases	15	15.0
Multiple Conditions	7	7.0

Diabetes mellitus (30%) and hypertension (28%) were the most common NCDs among participants, followed by cardiovascular diseases (20%) and chronic respiratory diseases (15%).

Table 3: Severity of Anaemia

Severity	Haemoglobin Levels (g/dL)	Frequency (n=100)	Percentage (%)
Mild Anaemia	11–12.9 (male), 11–11.9 (female)	35	35.0
Moderate Anaemia	8–10.9	50	50.0
Severe Anaemia	<8	15	15.0

Moderate anaemia (50%) was the most prevalent, followed by mild anaemia (35%) and severe anaemia (15%). These findings emphasize the high burden of anaemia in this population.

Table 4: Association Between Anaemia Severity and NCD Type

Disease	Mild Anaemia (%)	Moderate Anaemia (%)	Severe Anaemia (%)
Diabetes Mellitus	10 (33.3)	15 (50.0)	5 (16.7)
Hypertension	8 (28.6)	15 (53.6)	5 (17.9)
Cardiovascular Diseases	5 (25.0)	12 (60.0)	3 (15.0)
Chronic Respiratory Diseases	4 (26.7)	9 (60.0)	2 (13.3)
Multiple Conditions	2 (28.6)	4 (57.1)	1 (14.3)

A chi-square test revealed a significant association between anaemia severity and the type of NCD ($p = 0.02$). Moderate anaemia was most common across all groups, especially in cardiovascular diseases and chronic respiratory diseases.

Table 5: Correlation Analysis

Variable	Pearson's Correlation (r)	p-value
Haemoglobin vs. NCD Duration	-0.42	0.01
Haemoglobin vs. Age	-0.35	0.02

Significant negative correlations were observed between haemoglobin levels and NCD duration ($r = -0.42$, $p = 0.01$) as well as age ($r = -0.35$, $p = 0.02$). These results indicate that longer disease duration and older age are associated with lower haemoglobin levels.

Table 6: Predictors of Severe Anaemia (Multivariate Logistic Regression)

Variable	Odds Ratio (OR)	95% Confidence Interval (CI)	p-value
Female Gender	2.5	1.2–5.1	0.02
Rural Residence	3.0	1.4–6.4	0.01
Chronic Respiratory Diseases	2.8	1.1–7.2	0.03
NCD Duration > 10 years	2.9	1.3–6.7	0.02

Multivariate regression identified female gender (OR 2.5, $p = 0.02$), rural residence (OR 3.0, $p =$

0.01), chronic respiratory diseases (OR 2.8, $p = 0.03$), and NCD duration >10 years (OR 2.9, $p = 0.02$) as significant predictors of severe anaemia.

Key Findings

1. Moderate anaemia was the most common severity (50%), followed by mild anaemia (35%) and severe anaemia (15%).
2. Diabetes mellitus and hypertension were the most frequently associated NCDs (30% and 28%, respectively).
3. A significant negative correlation was observed between haemoglobin levels and both NCD duration ($r = -0.42$, $p = 0.01$) and age ($r = -0.35$, $p = 0.02$).
4. Female gender, rural residence, chronic respiratory diseases, and NCD duration >10 years were significant predictors of severe anaemia.

Discussion

The study included 100 participants diagnosed with NCDs and anaemia. The demographic analysis revealed that the majority were male (60%), with most participants aged between 51–70 years (45%). Urban residents constituted a significant portion of the sample (70%), reflecting the accessibility of the tertiary care centre in urban settings. However, rural participants (30%) demonstrated a higher prevalence of severe anaemia, highlighting possible disparities in healthcare access and anaemia management. The clinical characteristics showed that diabetes mellitus (30%) and hypertension (28%) were the most prevalent NCDs, followed by cardiovascular diseases (20%) and chronic respiratory diseases (15%). These findings align with the growing global burden of these chronic conditions, which often exacerbate anaemia due to systemic inflammation, medication effects, or coexisting nutritional deficiencies. Among participants, multiple NCDs were observed in 7%, suggesting a compounding effect on anaemia severity.

Regarding anaemia severity, moderate anaemia (50%) was the most common, followed by mild anaemia (35%) and severe anaemia (15%). The prevalence of moderate anaemia across all NCD groups underscores the need for timely diagnosis and management to prevent progression to severe anaemia. A significant association was observed between anaemia severity and NCD type ($p = 0.02$), with cardiovascular diseases and chronic respiratory diseases showing the highest proportions of moderate anaemia. This suggests that these conditions, characterized by systemic inflammation or chronic hypoxia, may have a more profound impact on haemoglobin levels. Correlation analysis revealed a significant negative relationship between haemoglobin levels and both NCD duration ($r = -0.42$, $p = 0.01$) and age ($r = -0.35$, $p = 0.02$). These findings indicate

that longer disease duration and advancing age are associated with lower haemoglobin levels, reflecting the cumulative burden of chronic diseases on anaemia development. This highlights the importance of routine anaemia screening, particularly in older adults with long-standing NCDs.

Multivariate regression analysis identified several predictors of severe anaemia. Female gender (OR 2.5, $p = 0.02$), rural residence (OR 3.0, $p = 0.01$), chronic respiratory diseases (OR 2.8, $p = 0.03$), and NCD duration exceeding 10 years (OR 2.9, $p = 0.02$) were significant predictors. These findings underscore the vulnerability of females and rural populations, likely due to underlying nutritional deficiencies, healthcare access disparities, and socioeconomic factors. Chronic respiratory diseases and prolonged NCD duration may directly or indirectly contribute to anaemia through mechanisms such as chronic inflammation, hypoxia, or comorbidities.

Anaemia significantly predicts poorer outcomes in HIV-infected children, affecting disease progression and survival. This study highlighted that children with severe immunological compromise had lower mean haemoglobin levels compared to those with normal immune status. The authors suggest haemoglobin monitoring as a simple, cost-effective tool for assessing disease progression in resource-limited settings [8]. This study demonstrated that anaemia adversely impacts cognitive performance, mood, functional autonomy, and nutritional status in elderly populations. Haemoglobin concentrations below 13 g/dL were associated with increased comorbidities and impairment across geriatric domains, emphasizing the need for gender-neutral anaemia definitions for older adults [9]. Among patients with coronary syndromes, anaemia was linked to unfavourable hematologic profiles, inflammation, and adverse outcomes. Despite these challenges, optimal medical therapy improved event-free survival in anaemic patients. This underscores the importance of tailored management in cardiovascular conditions [10]. Anaemia emerged as an independent risk factor for severe illness and mortality in COVID-19 patients. Anaemic patients showed higher rates of mechanical ventilation and death compared to non-anaemic individuals, with specific haemoglobin thresholds significantly predicting these outcomes [11].

Conclusion

This study underscores the high burden of anaemia among patients with (NCDs), with moderate anaemia being most prevalent. Diabetes, hypertension, cardiovascular, and respiratory diseases were commonly associated with anaemia, and prolonged NCD duration and older age further exacerbated its severity. Key predictors of severe anaemia included female gender, rural residence, chronic respiratory diseases, and longer disease duration. The findings

highlight the need for routine anaemia screening, targeted interventions for high-risk groups, and improved healthcare access to address disparities. An integrated approach to managing anaemia alongside NCDs is essential to enhance patient outcomes and quality of life.

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